

Method for mass-rearing the rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis*

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Although the rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* is widely distributed as a pest of rice in Asia, little is known about its ecology and control. The larvae of this pyralid moth possess tracheal gills and require water for survival. Damage is caused by the leaf-feeding larvae, which cut the tips of rice leaves to make tubular cases. Larvae float on the water surface in their cases during the day and at night climb up the rice plant and feed on leaves by scraping the leaf tissue and leaving white skeletonized feeding marks. Fields are infested only during the vegetative stage, from seeding to maximum tillering. Larval populations are often highly aggregated because water currents passing through paddies cause them to float downstream to lower-lying fields. This aggregative behavior has complicated chemical control trials and little is known about the effectiveness of various insecticides against this pest. Identification of possibly resistant cultivars has been hampered by lack of a rearing method for producing adequate numbers of caseworms for greenhouse screening.

Figure Procedure for mass-rearing the rice caseworm on rice plants in the greenhouse. IRRI, 1979

A mass-rearing method was developed to produce caseworms for insecticide and varietal resistance screening programs at IRRI (see figure). The rearing cycle begins with the adult. Four oviposition cage designs were tested in a non-airconditioned room offering a range of relative humidities (RH) to determine the optimal requirements for maximum egg production. Egg production was highest in an aerated cage design at 83-87% RH (see table). We used a mylar plastic cylinder cage (25-cm diameter and 54-cm high with mesh top, side windows, and sleeves) immersed in water. The females oviposited on the undersides of cut rice leaves floating on the water. About 30 10-cm-long leaves, cut from 3-week-old IR36 plants, were individually placed on the water leaving about 1-cm distance between them to provide room for females to oviposit. Forty pairs of moths, placed in the oviposition cage, produced about 5,400 eggs in 4 days. Neither sugar nor other sustenance for the moths increased egg production. The leaves were replaced every day; those with eggs were held in shallow egg-holding trays with the eggs submerged. Eggs hatched in 3 days and the larvae fed on the cut leaves. To maintain the culture, 3% of the eggs (about 160) were introduced into the larval rearing cage to produce the 80 adults.

The larval rearing cage is a wooden frame with mesh sides. It was set in a galvanized metal tray containing 12 cm water. Larvae pupated on the leaf sheaths in 17-20 days. At pupation, the pots containing eight plants each, were removed and placed in an adult emergence cage. The tops of the plants were cut so that the emerging moths would rest on the sides of the cage rather than on the plants and thus could readily be collected. The adults emerged in about 1 week.

Comparison of four oviposition cage designs for maximum case worm egg production. IRRI, 1979		
Cage design	Eggs/female (no.) ^{a/}	RH (%) inside cage ^{b/}
Nylon mesh (fully aerated)	105 a	83
Mylar plastic cylinder with top and side mesh	136 a	84
Mylar plastic cylinder with top mesh only	133 a	87
Mylar plastic cylinder (enclosed)	67 b	91
^{a/} Av of 5 replications, 15-18 females and 15-22 males/cage. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P <0.05).		
^{b/} Recorded at midday; ambient room RH = 76%.		

